

AFRICAI-RI Hardware & Data workflow Assessment form

The purpose of this questionnaire is to gather hardware and data workflow information from all participating clinical sites from the Sub Saharan African (SSA) institutions. This form will serve as the standard way of preliminary data collection to provide all sites a way to report in a uniform manner. The inputs will be further validated during 1-on-1 interviews with IT and data managers of each site.

This form will have three sections,

- **Section 1:** Contact information of all personnel who can attend a short interview
- **Section 2:** Hardware assessment of clinical site
- **Section 3:** Medical imaging data workflow assessment and adoption of standards

If any part of this form is ambiguous or needs further clarification, please do not hesitate to contact us.
(mail to m.birhanu@erasmusmc.nl).

* Indicates required question

1. **Name of Institution ***

Dropdown

Mark only one oval.

- CISM
- MRCCG
- UIDT
- IDRC
- JU
- CERMEL
- KUHES
- DIG
- NIMR
- UNIKIN

IT manager contact information

2. Full name *

3. Email *

Data manager contact information

4. Full name *

5. Email *

Hardware Assessment: Imaging Equipment and Modalities

This section includes information over all types of imaging modalities planned to be used in this project. This will cover instruments used to acquire retrospective data and those planned to be used to collect prospective data.

6. For retrospective data, can you give some information on X-ray and/or Ultrasound units used?
Please provide the Vendor, Model name (if available) and how many units used to image patients to give an indication of device variability.

7. In what format are the acquired images exported?

Mark only one oval.

- DICOM
- Image format (JPG/JPEG/PNG)
- Analog film images
- Other:

8. How are the acquired images stored? Does your institution use PACS for storing medical images?

Mark only one oval.

- Yes
- No
- Other:

9. If 'yes', can you provide the vendor and the model type of your PACS?

10. Do you have a vendor or third party support contracts for maintenance and technical support for your X-rays and PACS?

Mark only one oval.

Yes

No

Other

11. if 'other' please give more context and description here.

12. For prospective data, can you give some information on Ultrasound units planned to be used?

Please provide the Vendor and Model name (if available).

13. How are images stored for long term? Can you indicate which type of storage option is used?

Mark only one oval.

- Local storage server
- External disk storage
- Cloud virtual machine
- Other:

14. If you use a local storage server, do you have a data center/dedicated room for your servers?

Mark only one oval.

- Yes
- No
- Other:

15. Do you have contacts of hardware resellers and maintenance providers in your area (for future procurement process)

Mark only one oval.

- Yes
- No
- Other:

Hardware Assessment: IT, Network and Compute Infrastructure

16. What is the bandwidth of your internet network?

Mark only one oval.

- 1 - 50 Mbps
- 50 - 100 Mbps
- 100 - 200 Mbps
- 200 - 1Gbps
- > 1Gbps

17. What type of network does your institution use?

Mark only one oval.

- Fiber optics
- Satellite
- Other:

18. How stable is your connectivity? Do you experience loss of connection?

Mark only one oval.

- Stable
- Fairly stable
- Not stable
- Other:

19. Do you make use of alternative internet providers in case of loss of connectivity?

Mark only one oval.

Yes

No

Other:

20. Do you experience power outage/electricity cuts? What is the frequency of your power outage experience? choose 'None' if you do not experience any or if you have a UPS system already in place.

Mark only one oval.

None

In a matter of hours

Daily

Weekly

Monthly

Yearly

21. Is there a firewall behind the hospital network? In other words, is the research data storage protected by a hospital network?

Mark only one oval.

Yes

No

Other:

22. Is external access restricted from all hospital network ports?

Mark only one oval.

- Yes
- No

23. Does your institution or research group make use of GPU workstation / GPU cluster for analysis?

Mark only one oval.

- Yes
- No
- Other:

Data Workflow Assessment: acquisition, linkage, access and storage

24. Can your scanners (X-ray or Ultrasound machines) connect to a PACS or Radiology Information System (RIS) for automated data flow?

Mark only one oval.

- Yes
- No
- Other:

25. If you have any analog/film images, can you explain what procedure you use to store the data along with the digital images?

26. Does your institution use Electronic Health Record (EHR) systems to manage longitudinal patient clinical data?

Mark only one oval.

Yes

No

Other:

27. if 'yes', which platform of EHR is used?

28. How is patient clinical data exported for research?

Mark only one oval.

Automated export from the ECRs

Manual export

Other:

29. Do you plan to use electronic Case Report Form (CRFs) to collect all study related data in this research study?

Mark only one oval.

Yes

No

Other:

30. If 'yes', which eCRF platform do you (plan to) use?

31. How is imaging data linked to clinical data?

Mark only one oval.

Look Up Tables for pseudo-anonimized ID

Direct Patient ID

Other:

32. What type of anonymization do you use for research data? You can fill out 'None' if this does not apply to your institution.

33. Do you have a dedicated data manager(s) to perform the task of data linkage, validation and cleaning for this project?

Mark only one oval.

Yes

No

34. Do you have storage backup routines and retention policy?

Mark only one oval.

Yes

No

Other:

35. What are the manual steps where staff needs to fill in information by hand to your Patient record / data management system? This helps us to understand data workflow in your institution.

Data Workflow Assessment: standards and interoperability

36. Does our institution have any specific anonymization requirement? (e.g list of DICOM headers)

Mark only one oval.

Yes

No

Other:

37. If 'Yes', please elaborate what they are here.

38. Are there any standards vocabularies/terminologies that the data you provide complies to? check all that apply.

Check all that apply.

None

SNOMED-CT

ICD

RadLex

LOINC

Other: _____

39. Do you (plan to) document the data cleaning and validation processes performed?

Mark only one oval.

Yes

No

Other: _____

40. Are you using any standard data model? check all that apply.

Check all that apply.

OMOP (Observational Medical Outcomes Partnership)

FHIR (Fast Health Interoperability Resources)

DICOM

Other: _____

Consent

Thank you for your patience in filling out this questionnaire.

By submitting this form, you consent to the inclusion of your information in our research survey. The data you provide will be used solely for the purpose of analyzing your responses and offering appropriate support based on the information submitted.

41. Click the button below to agree in giving your consent. *

Mark only one oval.

I agree.

Google Forms

